

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B150
Date: 15 Dec 2005
Take Off: 10:22:24
Landing: 15:22:45
Flight Time: 5h00m21

Campaign: Cirrus
Operating Area: Chilbolton

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	First Officer	Steve Ball	FAAM
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Clare Lee	Met Office
5	Flight Manger	Maureen Smith	FAAM
6	Cloud physics	Paul James	FAAM
7	Dropsondes	Steve Devereau	FAAM
8	ARIES / MARSS / DEIMOS	Stuart Rogers	Met Office
9	Mission Scientist 2	Stuart Newman	Met Office
10	SWS	Dave Kindred	Met Office
11	CCN / CCM2	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
12	CCN Training	Richard Cotton	Met Office
13	TAFTS	Paul Green	ICL
14	TAFTS	Maxwell Bolton	ICL
15	CPI	Hazel Jones	Manchester University
16			
17			
18			
19			

Flight Track:

B150 Track 15-DEC-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b150
 Date: 15 Dec 2005
 Project: Cirrus
 Location: Chilbolton

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
100827		Position	0.04 kft	124	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W
100945		INU	0.04 kft	124	To Navigate
102224		T/O	1.4 kft	329	Cranfield
102833		ASPs	10.8 kft	325	Open
103709		Videos	11.0 kft	252	Start FFC & DFC
105815	110443	Profile 1	5.0 - 0.71 kft	259	Q1022 5k'to 1k'
110444	110725	Profile 2	0.71 - 2.2 kft	282	1k' to 2k'
110953	112112	Profile 2	2.3 - 10.0 kft	048	From 2k'
111650		Event	5.8 kft	068	1000fpm from 5k'
112303	113227	Profile 2	10.0 - 19.0 kft	286	
113648	114358	Profile 2	19.0 - 26.0 kft	076	
114225		Video	24.4 kft	066	Change tapes
114515	115200	Run 1.1	26.0 kft	066	
114935		Event	26.0 kft	066	Ovhd Chilbolton
115534	120647	Run 1.2	26.0 kft	294	Westbound
121201	121701	Run 1.3	26.0 kft	042	
121737	121914	Orbit 1	26.1 - 25.9 kft	048	50 left, start 020
122048	122228	Orbit 2	26.0 - 25.9 kft	339	50 left, start 320
122440	122615	Orbit 3	26.1 - 25.9 kft	249	50 left, start 240
122759	123801	Run 1.3	26.0 kft	065	
123621		Event	26.0 kft	054	Ovhd Chilbolton
124253	125113	Profile 3	26.0 - 31.0 kft	273	
125740	125946	Profile 3	31.0 - 33.0 kft	048	
125839		Video	32.3 kft	052	St DFC Tape3
125953	130847	Run 2.1	33.0 - 33.1 kft	060	
130503		Event	33.0 kft	064	Contrails on RFC
130711		Event	33.1 kft	067	Ovhd Chilbolton
131345		Event	33.0 kft	291	Ovhd Chilbolton
131418	131549	Profile 4	33.1 - 34.0 kft	263	
132220		Sonde	34.0 kft	264	Launch #01
132303	132304	Run 3.1	34.0 kft	280	
132926		Event	34.0 kft	042	Thru our contrail
133001	133304	Profile 5	34.0 - 35.0 kft	066	
133304	134005	Run 4.1	35.0 kft	067	
133849		Event	35.0 kft	055	Ovhd Chilbolton
134633		Event	35.1 kft	265	Ovhd Chilbolton
134642	135514	Run 4.2	35.1 - 35.0 kft	262	
140131	140812	Profile 6	35.0 - 29.0 kft	052	
140539		Event	31.2 kft	064	No contrails
141001	141319	Profile 6	29.0 - 26.0 kft	266	
141704	141823	Orbit 4	26.0 kft	038	55 left, start 030
141957	142131	Orbit 5	26.0 - 25.9 kft	326	50 left, start 350
142300	142427	Orbit 6	26.0 kft	258	50 left, start 240
142534	142819	Profile 7	26.1 - 23.0 kft	278	1000fpm
143355	144237	Profile 7	23.0 - 20.2 kft	090	1500fpm from FL205
144450	144903	Profile 7	9.9 - 4.8 kft	287	1000fpm
145901		ASPs	10.0 kft	345	Close
152245		Land	0.12 kft	212	Cranfield
152620		Position	0.10 kft	307	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W

B150 Track 15-DEC-05

CAESAR SORTIE BRIEF

Cirrus in-situ measurements for radar validation

B150 – 15th December 2005

Aim

The aim is to study the in-situ properties of cirrus over land, co-ordinated with the Chilbolton radars/lidars and coincident with an overpass of the CloudSat-Aqua train. The priority is to obtain in-situ microphysical measurements from straight and levels runs at several levels within the cloud and profiles between so that the statistical properties of the cloud are well characterized in order to validate the radar measurements. A few runs above the cloud are to be made for radiative measurements during the satellite overpass. The exact location and duration of the runs are to be determined from the cirrus location and its advection due to the wind.

Weather

Cirrus, ideally with clear skies below. Some cloud below is acceptable, as long as the cirrus is measurable by the radar.

Operating region

Runs and profiles are expected to take place along a fixed radial from the Chilbolton Meteorological Observatory (51 08' 36" N 01 26' 02" W) at the location of the cirrus, ideally into and with the wind direction. Note, the 35GHz radar and lidar have a fixed vertical view and hence measurements directly over the site are critical. Only the 3GHz is steerable during CAESAR 1.

Clearances

Clearances will be required for dropping sondes and performing a profile from minimum allowable altitude.

Communications

With operators at Chilbolton via SATCOM or VHF radio (130.575 MHz, call-sign "Radsearch").

		Manoeuvre	Duration (min)
1	10:30	Takeoff from Cranfield and Transit at appropriate level to enter operating area at min altitude	45
2	11:15	Profile ascent from minimum altitude to cloud top or to max altitude at 1000ft/min	35
3	11:50	Perform a series of reciprocal straight and level runs at several levels within the cloud, with profile descents between each level.	70
4	13:00	Profile ascent to max altitude	10
5	13:10	1 straight and level run above cloud. Drop 1 sonde.	10
6	13:15	Satellite overpass during run.	
7	13:20	Reciprocal straight and level run.	10
8	13:30	Perform a series of reciprocal straight and level runs at several levels within the cloud, with profile descents between each level.	55
9	14:25	Profile descent to min altitude at 1000ft/min	35
10	15:00	Transit to Cranfield	45
11	15:45	Land Cranfield	Total 315

Requirements for ARIES and SWS

In the cloud:

ARIES: nadir with calcs every 2 minutes ideally during turns

SWS: series of viewing angles during every run with appropriate calcs (measurements to be used to test Robin Hogan's 3D stochastic model) - see extra guidance sheet.

Above cloud:

1st run above cloud

ARIES & SWS both viewing nadir. Calibrations to be coordinated such that both instruments simultaneously view the cloud for the maximum time.

2nd run above cloud

ARIES & SWS both viewing nadir **then** for last 2 minutes both viewing zenith .

Mission Scientist Debrief

B150 – 15th December 2005

CAESAR sortie over Chilbolton

Mission scientist – Clare Lee

The weather conditions were a thin sheet of cirrus flowing from the North, with small patches of Cu and occasionally hazy at low levels. Legs with procedural turns were made along 253 radial to and over Chilbolton, with fixed ground positions approximately cross wind. Radio contact with Chilbolton worked well. Contrails were observed above FL330 and engine settings noted.

The transit from Cranfield was made at FL100 followed by a descent to 5000ft into the operating area. A profile descent (P1) was made to 1000ft (min altitude over land), followed immediately by an interrupted profile ascent to FL260. A run (R1.1) was flown towards Chilbolton below the cirrus, followed by a reciprocal run. Both runs flew directly overhead of Chilbolton. The reciprocal run (R1.3) was interrupted to perform three 50 degree banking angle left handed orbits below variable amounts of cirrus. The run (R1.3) towards Chilbolton was recommenced. The cirrus was very thin but 8/8, with variable thin Cu below. An interrupted profile climb (P3) was made to FL330. At FL310 2D measured some ice particles. Near the end of the following run (R2.1) at FL330 CPI observed a few ice crystals. A profile to FL340 was made, followed by a run (R3.1). Some low concentrations of ice were seen periodically by 2DC. At 132220 a dropsonde was launched at a similar time to the AQUA overpass (1310). A profile ascent (P5) to FL350 was made, followed by reciprocal runs (R4) in the cirrus. Both CPI and 2DC observed ice crystals, though intermittently and in low concentrations. An interrupted profile descent (P6) to FL260 was made, during which the contrails ceased. Three left handed 50 degree banked orbits were performed at FL260, which extremely thin cirrus above. An interrupted profile descent to was made to 5000ft to characterize the atmosphere. The aircraft transited back to Cranfield.

Instrument status

TAFTS - U/S

SWS - OK

SID1 - U/S, except for short time at beginning of flight

ARIES - OK, except intermittent periods of scanning slowly

Chilbolton Raman lidar – U/S

CPI – OK, except last 2 minutes

2D – OK

PCASP – high noise in first 2 channels but can be recovered

FWVS – OK

AVAPS – 1 sone OK

MARSS – OK (monitored by Stuart Rogers)

Deimos – not operated

BBR – OK

TWC - OK

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.150**
FAAM © 2004

Date **15/12/05**

Page **1** of **9**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:30					Take off Cranfield
		F1100			Transit. Asked SWST APRES view ↑
10 39 25		F2100	256		Descent to operating area. Very thin Ci ~ 419 @ 6000ft.
104340		5000ft.	170		
104720		5000ft.	169		Hazy below, 78 Ci above.
105039					TARTS reporting failure. SWST reporting increase in signal - corresponding to increase in cloud above + thickness
					Hazy below 78 Ci above.
105751			259		Can see gap in Ci far ahead.
1058 50 ⁵⁵	P1	5000ft.			profile descent to 1000ft. wind: 8ms' / 347° v. small patches of Ci to right + left. thicker cloud on horizon.
110444	P1 end	900ft.			fo 1022mb.
	P2	1000ft.	280		Ascent.
110725	P2 int.	2500ft.			Intercept profile thin Ci above. ~ 519.
110953	P2 rec.	2500ft.	058	50.8/2.8	recommence profile. Ci thicker to E. Hazy around

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B** B150.....

Date 15/12/05.....

Page 2 of 9.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
111530					SIDI keeps washing ARIES warning at wrong speed taking 2x's time to scan Start trying to correct.
112112	P2int	FL100	70	51.0/1.8	intercepting turning right.
112303	P2rec	FL100	283	51.0/1.8	recommencing profile 6/8 Ci above.
	Chilbolton report.				SAt St. (Cst: 35kt. Thr. ~24kt?)
113035					SIDI now back on. FWWS now on.
113227	P3int	FL 190		50.8/2.9	doing procedural turns. Wind 18ms ⁻¹ / 320° 6/8 W below, 4/8 Ci above.
113521					ARIES reporting improvement - but still switch to slow speed intermittently.
113830					SIDI failed again.
113648	P2rec	FL190 FL215	066	50.8/2.9	recommencing profile. Wind 19ms ⁻¹ / 330°
				50.9/2.6W	T - 26.17, TD - 39.73 Hazy below.
		FL230		50.9/2.5	T - 29.7, TD - 35.15
	Chilbolton report				778km

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.150**.....

 Date **15/12/03**.....

 Page **3** of **9**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
114358	P2 ^{end}	FL260	66		
	R1.1	FL260			Run start
114934	P2	FL260	54	51°11.3	Over head Chilbolton
115124	R1.1 ^{end}				Turning right wind 23ms ⁻¹ 1348° T-37 → T ₀ -43
115534	R1.2	FL260	275	51°11.5	Over head Chilbolton.
115817					No W below; broken W all around ~ 4/8 max in places. Ci thinning above.
120422		FL260	264	50°9'12.6	thicker W to SW thin Ci above ~ 7/8 SWS spectral peak increasing during run.
120647	R1.2 ^{end}	FL260		50°8'12.9	End run. turning right for procedural turn. (25° bank angle). Thin W below ~ 4/8 + haze increasing to S.
121201	R1.3	FL260	043	50°8'12.9W	Start Run. Some thin cloud to right ~ FL250 1/8 W below, 7/8 Ci above.
121701	R1.3 ^{int.}	FL260	066	50°9'12.2	Intercept for orbits.
121737	O1	FL260	072		Orbit at 50° 01.3 4/8 W below, within Ci above ~ 8/8 Wind 30ms ⁻¹ 118°

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B...150**.....

 Date **14/12/05**.....

 Page **4** of **9**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
121940	01end	FL260	003	50.9/2.2	End of orbit.
122048	02st.	FL260	340		50° bank angle.
122226	02end.	FL260		51.0/2.2	Heading towards thicker Ci
			276		to W.
					T-37.4 → T _D -42.3
122440	03	FL260	240	51.0/2.5	Ci slightly thicker than before above, but still thin ~ 1/8 ^{7.38} W below.
122615	03end	FL260		50.9/2.5	
122759	R1 ³ ca	FL260	056	50.9/2.5	Recommencing run towards Chilbolton.
					Variable thin W below
					Ci slightly thicker to North.
123621					Over Chilbolton.
					Report thick so Ci been seen.
					We can see Ci visually though. Thin 3/8.
					SWS showing Ci above.
123801	R1.3end	FL260			End of run.
					Thicker W out to W E.
124225		FL260	283		Over top of Chilbolton.
124253	P3	FL260	266	51.1/1.5	Profile climb to FL330
125113	P3int.	FL310	266	50.9/2.6	Turning procedural to right then left no W below though may Ci above v. thin

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B...150.....**

 Date **14/12/05**

 Page **5** of **9**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
125420					2D probing up 35→40µm particles during turn.
		FL310		510, 3.0W	T = -50.7, T _D = -50.14
					Winds 21ms ⁻¹ / 2°
125609					3/4 W below.
					Li varying in thickness above.
125740	P3rec	FL310	51	508/2.7	profile recurrence.
130702					LPL saw few crystals
130711		FL330			Over Chilbolton.
125846	P3end	FL330	060		profile end.
	R2.1st	FL330			Run at FL330 start.
130847	R2.1end	FL330			Turning right.
					wind 23ms ⁻¹ 134°
					T - 55.43, T _D - 53.85.
		FL330			Contrailing at FL330
					engines N1 96.0
					TGT 735 → 764
					N2 90.3
					FF/FV 5.4 → 5.5
1313		FL330			Over Chilbolton.
131418	P4st		259	511/1.5	Profile to FL340
131549	P4end	FL340			
"	R3.1	FL340	264		wind 33ms ⁻¹ 1339°
		FL340			Contrailing.
					N1 90, TGT 704 → 674
					N2 87.3, FF/FV, 4.4

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B**.....150.....

 Date14/12/05.....

 Page 6 of 9

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
132003		FZ340	264	50° 12.4W	2D seeing v. low conc. for short time ~10cc. 25µm or less
132230	S1	FZ340	264	50° 12.7W	Drysonde - Good.
132304	R3/1st	FZ340			End of run. procedural turn busy below. v. thin G above. can see contrails we produced. on left.
132824					Heading towards contrail
132940					2D saw something for short time whilst going thro' contrail.
133001	PS	FZ340	364	50° 12.6W	Climbing to FZ350. Wind 32 ms ⁻¹ / 350° T - 60.25, T _D - 55.66
133304	PS end	FZ350	067	50° 12.1W	End profile
" "	R4.1	FZ350	067		Start run.
133350					CP1 seeing few crystals not very big columns.
133458					Drysonde hit ground.
133545					CP1 - bullet rosette ~100µm 2D small concs, small sizes.
133840?					Over Chilbolton. Not seeing much.
					Update from Chilbolton - can't see on radar or lidar

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.150**.....

 Date **14/12/05**.....

 Page **7** of **9**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
134005	R4.1	FL350		51.1/1.2W	End of run. Turning right. W thickening to W E. (7/8) (SWS seeing 35-55 units. - large variability in Ci above)
134359		FL350	319	51.0/1.2W	Thin above, thicker ahead to W. W ~ 3/8 below. Still no SIDD - won't report. Over Chilton.
134628					
134642	R4.2	FL350			Start run clear slot ahead + to North.
135032					2D seeing low conc + small particles. Contrailing
		FL350			N1 93.3, TKT 729 → 701 N2 88.7, F91FV 47 Wind: 3/m/s 1339°, 59knts 1344° T - 60.66, T _D - 57.14 No Ci above or v. thin Ci
135514	R4.2	FL350			SWS seeing ~ 35 max peak. Turning to right then left. Hazy below + above, no W Can see contrails. larger amounts W to S.
135954					Hazy below, wisps of Ci (contrail) above.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.150**.....

 Date **14/12/05**.....

 Page **8** of **9**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
140131	P6	F2350	056	50.8/1.7W	Profile descent to F2260 contrails stopped
140513		31320	063	50.9/2.1	M170 620 TET. } M 80.9, 2.9 (FF/FV) }
140812	P6 int	F2290		51.0/1.8W	interrupt profile turning left (~40° bank angle)
141001	P6 rec.	F2290		51.0/1.9W	recommence profile.
141319	P6 end	F2260		51.0N/2.4W	Turning left. thin patches w above hazy below.
141704	04	F2260	030		left hand orbit. ^{50°} bank the v.v. thin at G or none. more to S. + N.
141823	04 end				< 1/2 W below.
141957	05	F2260	350	50.9/2.1W	left hand orbit. 50°
142131	05 end	F2260			
142300	06	F2260	240	50.9/2.4W	left hand orbit 50°
142427	06 end	F2260	280		
142534	P7	F2260			Profile descent
142819	P7 int	F2230			procedural turn to the right then left.
143355	P7 rec.	F2230	087		Profile descent recommence at 1500 ft. min G the heavy above + ahead.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.140**.....

Date **14/12/05**.....

Page **9** of **9**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
144237	P7int.	FZ100		51°0'1.9W	intercept profile descent
144450	P7inc.	FZ100	288	50°9'2.0W	profile at 2000ft/min
144903	P7end	5000ft.	328	51°1'2.2W	end of profile descent
					Transit back to Cardiff
					ETA landing 1535
					Inst. status
					SWs - OK.
					PRIES - OK
					MARCS - OK.
					UPI - OK except lost 2 mins
					2D - all OK except
					SIDI 2 PCSP high
					noise in fit 2 channels but
					can be recovered.
					FNIS - All OK.
					AVAPS - 1 sonde OK.
					TAFIS - U/S.
					BSR - OK. TWC - OK.
					Chilbolton - all OK.
					except main radar - U/S.

ARIES flight log

Flight: B150

Location: Ch:7/bolton

page 1 of 4

Date: 15/Dec/2005

Operator(s): S. ROGERS

Resolution: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments	
09 00	On the ground	Power up	OK.								
09 09 00	"	B150A	C	71	31	15	-189.9	19.6	CH1 x1		
09 10 23	"	B	O	71.2	30.4	15.5		19.7	Z1 x3		
09 13 30		C	E						CH1 x1		
~10 25	Takeoff	_____								Take off PC time = Horace Time - 2 seconds	
10 37 17	Transit	B150D	C	70.9	30.5	11.4	-189.9	22.4	CH1 x1		
10 39 06		E	O	70.5	30.7	10.6		21.4	Z1 x2	Some banking at start (descending?)	
10 42 41		F	C	71.1	30.2	9.8		19.4	CH1 x1	← pause time (locking up)	
10 44 23		G	O	70.4	30.7	10.1	-190.6	20.1	Z1 x2	← pause time (locking at CBB)	
10 47 46		H	C	71.1	30.8	12.6		19.4	CH1 x1		
10 49 25	5000ft?	I	(C)O	70.6	30.8	12.6		19.9	Z1 x2 ←?	Some banking	
10 53 55		J	C	70.9	31.8	13.3		19.2	CH1 x1	"60 scans/min" ?!	
		- seems to be running slow - B150J took 2 mins rather than one. Restarting (Rebooting)									
10 59 03	PI ↓	B150K	C	71.1	30.7	14.1	-190.6	20.7	CH1 x1	"60 scans/min" during Cas	
10 01 24		L	O	70.4	30.9	13.7		20.6	Z1 x2	60 (20 during Hsq)	
10 06 35		M	C	71.3	30.6	13.7		19.0	CH1 x1	60	
		- still having problem - rebooting again									

ARIES flight log

Flight: B150

Location:

page 2 of 4

Date: 15 / Dec / 2005

Operator(s):

Resolution:

Gain A:

B:

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
11 44 43	FL26-	B150N	C	60.9	14.5	1.2	-190.6	19.5	CH1x1	120
11 46 04		B150O	O						Z1x2	
11 48 58		B150P	C	60.8	12.7	-6.3		14.2	CH1x1	Some banking. (end of run)
11 50 56		B150Q	C	60.8	11.4	-6.6		16.4	Z1x2 CH1x1	
11 54 42	R1-2	B150R	C	60.9	8.3	-7.7	-190.6	19.1	Z1x2 CH1x1	120
11 56 08		B150S	C/O	60.6	8.2	-8.1	"	19.3	Z1x2	
11 59 01		B150T	C	60.7	6.0	-11.6	"	14.3	CH1x1	
12 00 10		B150U	C/O	60.7	5.4	-11.4	"	15.9	Z1x2	
12 03 01		B150V	C	60.8	3.6	-13.1	"	14.0	CH1x1	
12 04 09		B150W	C/O	60.6	3.5	-13.1		15.6	Z1x1	
12 06 14		B150X	C	60.9	2.6	-14.0		15.2	CH1x1	End of run/banking
12 12 12	R1-3	B C150A	C	60.9	2.6	-13.5		19.6	CH1x1	
12 13 23		C150B	O	60.3	2.4	-14.2		19.1	Z1x2	
12 16 48		C150C	C	60.5	2.8	-15.5		14.1	CH1x1	
12 18 05	O1	C150D	O	60.6	2.5			15.9	Z1x2	← No PAUSE! End orbit before end of 2
12 20 09	O2	C150E	C	61.1	2.8				CH1x1	
12 21 19		C150F	O	60.5	2.6	-15.7		14.1	Z1x2	← End orbit before end of 2
12 23 24		C150G	C	61.1	2.8	-16.2		11.6	CH1x1	
12 24 39	O3	C150H	C/O	61.1					Z1x2	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B150

Location:

page 3 of 4

Date: 15 Dec 2005

Operator(s):

Resolution:

Gain A:

B:

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
12 27 40	R1.3 re-run	C150 J	C	60.8	2.4	-15.2	-18.9	15.0	CH1 x1	13.0
12 28 57		C150 J	O	60.6	2.7	-15.3		16.3	Z1 x2	
12 31 57		C150 K	C	60.8	2.6	-16.2		14.4	CH1 x1	
12 33 17		C150 L	O	60.6	2.8	-15.8		15.8	Z1 x2	
12 36 26		C150 M	C	61.0	2.8	-16.6		12.4	CH1 x1	
12 38		C150 N	C	60.9	2.7	-16.0		15.7	CH1 x1	
12 41 26		C150 O	C	60.9	2.9	-15.6		18.6	CH1 x1	
	P↑ to FL330									
13 02 03		C150 P	C	60.8	2.3	-18.1		16.9	CH1 x1	
13 03 24		C150 Q	O	60.2	3.0	-19.2	-19.6	15.9	Z1 x2	
13 06 32		C150 R	C	60.9	2.6	-23.2		10.9	CH1 x1	
13 08 00	Turning	C150 S	C/O	60.5	2.2	-23.0		12.7	Z1 x2	End of run 13:08:47 Turning
13 10 02		C150 T	C	61.0	2.8	-25.9	"	8.3	CH1 x1	No pause
13 11 30		C150 U	C	60.8	2.6	-25.0		11.5	CH1 x1	
13 13 40	P↑ to FL340	C150 V	O	60.2	2.7	-25.1		13.8	Z1 x2	Satellite overpass 13:15
13 16 40	FL340	C150 W	C	61.0	3.7!	-26.6		12.0	CH1 x1	
13 18 27		C150 X	O	60.5	2.7	-26.7		13.7	Z1 x2	
13 21 21		C150 Y	C	60.8	2.8	-27.7		12.1	CH1 x1	
13 22 39		C150 Z	C/O	60.5	2.7	-27.4		14.1	Z1 x2	End of run

ARIES flight log

Flight: BLS0

Location:

page 4 of 4

Date: 15/Dec/05

Operator(s):

Resolution:

Gain A:

B:

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
13 26		Restart	software	pre-	crash					
13 33 18	FL350 R4.1	D150A	C	70.5	31.4	-27.4	-190.6	18.6	CH1 x1	
13 34 38		D150B	O	69.9	30.3	-28.2		17.9	Z1 x2	
13 37 42		D150C	C	70.8	30.3	-30.2	-189	11.1	CH1 x1	
13 39		D150D	C/O	70.6	30.7	-29		13.2	Z1 x2	End of run 13 40 05
13 42 26		D150E	C	71.0	30.3	-30.		12.5	CH1 x1	
13 46 40	R4.2	D150F	C	70.4	30.3	-29		17.5	CH1 x1	
13 48 26		D150G	O	70.1	30.7	-29		17.6	Z1 x2	
13 57 33		D150H	C	70.6	30.5	-30	4	12.6	CH1 x1	
13 52 52		D150I	O	70.0	30.6	-30		13.9	Z1 x2	
13 55 50		D150J	C	70.6	31.4	-30		11.9	CH1 x1	
	P6 ↓ FL280									
14 13 41		D150K	C	71.6	30.3	-26		16.2	CH1 x1	
14 17 05	O4 50°	D150L	O	70	30	-24		14	Z1 x2	
14 19 09		D150M	C	70	30	-22		9.7	CH1 x1	← NO PAUSE
14 20 23	O5	D150N	O	70	29.8	-21		11.1	Z1 x1	
14 21 35		D150O	C	70	30	-20		9.4	CH1 x1	← NO PAUSE
14 23 01	O6	D150P	O	70	31	-20		11.3	Z1 x2	
14 26 01	P7 ↓	D150Q	C	70.6	30.4	-18.2		11.4	CH1 x1	

CHILBOLTON / CAESAR.

[20k WASCAT +1]
 SEC FROM
 HORIZ TIME]

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 150	Date	15/12/05		Operator(s)	JRK		log page	1	of	7
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks					
				Vis	NIR						

091414											→ SET SWS TO SYNCH. WITH HORIZ TIME.
1010											Starting Forward. [SWS TEMP +13°C] SWS Pre Flight checks ✓OK.
1012	Pre T/O.	—	000 (M)	500ms	1000ms						Sample period 0.1 sec. [Stopped until after T/O]
→ 102225											T/O Cleared
102328											Dark Current view [Sample period 0.10 Sec]
102340	TRANSIT	—	006 (F)	250ms	750ms						SWS Running now.
102557											Dark current view
102615	TRANSIT	7.3kft	006 (F)	900ms	1000ms						Start Running [+13°C]
→ 102928	SWS CAMERA	'ON'	(LP)								✓OK 7/8 Ci above, Small patches Sc below.
103812	TRANSIT	10.9kft	006 (F)	500ms	1000ms						Dark current view [+13°C]
103824	TRANSIT		↑	"	"						Running
104040	TRANSIT.		"	"	"						Vis Peaks up to 240k IR < 10000.
1042											→ 7/8 Ci above (mainly thin) 7/8 layer Sc below (mainly to SE).
104738	"	5.0kft	006 (F)	350ms	1000ms						Dark current cal
104759	"	5.0kft	↑	"	"						Running [* Just clipping 100 reduce wing time]
1051.											[Ci overhead has increased & thickened over last 10 mins - corresponds with Vis & IR spectra signals increasing] [+14°C] ALL RELTIES ON
105658	TRANSIT	8.0kft	006 (F)	350ms	1000ms						Dark current view / cal
105709	"		"	"	"						Running
105815	P1 START	FL050	006 (F)	350ms	1000ms						Start P1 ↓ 1000'. [+14°C]
110341				500	1000ms						Dark current view (changed in error to 250ms for Vis)
110356				"	"						Running (x2) first time.
110444	SWS P1/START P2	1000'	006 (F)	500ms	1000ms						Change from ↓ to ↑ profile [+13°C]

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 150	Date	15/12/05	Operator(s)	DK	log page	2 of 7
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	MIRR Pos	Int Times		Remarks	
				Vis	NIR		

110725	P2 ↗	2500'	006(F)	500ms	1000ms	Interrupt P2 ↗ ↖ auto reciprocal. (Few patches S below, otherwise Ci above)
110953	P2 ↗	2500'	"	"	"	Recommence P2 (500'/min)
111105			006(F)	350ms	1000ms	Start running Dark Current Cal
111117			↑	"	"	Start running
111300	Passing	3.5kft.				
111620		5000'				Change to 1000'/min SWS Temp +12, Petters 122 off
111910						Wind 359° / 11 m/sec LHRACE.
112112	P2 ↗	FL100	006(F)	350ms	1000ms	Interrupt P2, turn ↘
1126	⇒					⊙ Seeing Flow/size data now. (on Horace, & on PC?)
112649			006(F)	350ms	1000ms	Dark Current Cal
112700	P2 ↗		↑	"	"	Start running [+14°C ALL Petters ON]
						After work by Jim C on ground.
						⊙ Total Water Content VOK (After maintenance)
						⊙ BBR - will check in S4L
						⊙ SID 1 now back serviceable
						⊙ TAFTS - u/s (for flight)
						⊙ ARIES - slower response than usual
113227	P2 ↗	FL190	006(F)	350ms	1000ms	Interrupt P2 ↗ ↘ turn ↘
113630	→		↑			'Lost' SID 1 again!
113648	P2 ↗	FL190	"	"	"	Recommence P2
114038			006(F)	400ms	1000ms	Dark Current Cal
114049	P2 ↗	23.1kft	↑	"	"	Start running [+13°C]
114358	End P2	FL260	"	"	"	End P2 [7/8 Cs above]
						COINCIDENTAL
						Start R1.1
114455			"	500ms	1000ms	Dark Cal (Sample Period)
114507			"	"	"	RUN
114525			"	750ms	1000ms	Dark Cal
114938			"	"	"	RUN [+13°C]
114934	R1	25.9kft				END R1.1 o/h CHEBLT. [No sign of being included from C-Physics]

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B150	Date	15/12/05	Operator(s)	DRK	log page	3	of	7
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks			
				Vis	NIR				

115130									Now turning ↻ that back to Chubb
	START								
115834	1.2	FL260	006 (F)	750ms	1000ms	Start R 1.2			(PCASP not working well)
			↑						
115746	1.2		"	"	"	Dark current view			[Temp +12°C 122 Filters off]
115757	"		"	"	"	Start Run			
120647	1.2	FL260	"	"	"	End Run 1.2			Turn ↻ at W end of leg.
120721			006 (F)	750	1000ms	Dark current view			(Fluorescence)
120732			↑			Run			looks OK ✓
121201	1.3	FL260	006 (F)	750ms	1000ms	Start Run 1.3			
			↑						
121347	"	"	"	"	"	Dark current view			[+14 All Particles]
121359	"	"	"	"	"	'Run' Measurement			
121607	1.3	FL260	"	"	"	Dark current view			
121217			"	"	"	'Run' Measurement			
121701						Interrupt 1.3			
121737	Start orbit 1		"	750	1000	Start orbit (50°)			(initially 020 Hg)
	(clipping end at 210°)					Make it clipping on VIS.			
121940	End orbit 1					End orbit 1			
121941			"	200	1000	Dark Cal			
121953						Measurement			
122548	Start orbit 2		006 (F)	200	1000	Start orbit 2			(Hdg 340°)
									(Up to a SS k on VIS)
122228	End orbit 2					End orbit 2			
122321						Start orbit 1 Start Dark Cal.			
122329			006	200ms	500ms	Start Run			
122440	Orbit 3		006	200	500	Start orbit 3 (50°)			[+14°]
122615	←		00 "	"	"	End orbit 3 (50°)			
122637			"	200	500	Start Dark Cal			
122657			"	"	"	Measure			

Solar Zenith Angle ~ 16° (15.7° more exact)

86R ✓

lower than
" P/ages
a little
noisy

but others good.

Fluorescence
NV sense

TWC ✓

✓ All looking
good.

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 150	Date	15/12/05	Operator(s)	DKK	log page	4	of	7
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks			
				Vis	NIR				

(Sampling Periods ALL 0-10 sec)

122759	START R 1-3									SWS Temp.	
122804			006 F	400	1000	Dark view				[+14C]	
122818			↑	"	"	Start measurement					
123041	R 1-3	FL360	"	500	1000	Dark view					
123053						← Start running/measurement					
123230	"	"	006 F	750	1000	Dark view				[+13C]	
123243	"	"	↑			Start running					
123620						(Vis values peaking 50-55k)					
123621			→			o/h Chilbolton					
12380						End R 1-3, Turning ↘					
124232			→			o/h Chilbolton					
124218			"	"	"	Dark view					
12428			"	"	"	Start running					
124253	START P3 ↗	260	006 F	750	1000	Start P3 ↗ FL260 x FL330					
1249			↑			SWS Temp = 12°C (Peltiers 1/2 off)					
125113	P3 inter	FL310	006 F	750ms	1000ms	Interrupt P3 & Turn ↘					
			↑			C ₁ /C _s still well above this level.					
125415			→			2DC 25µm-40µm picking up small/few particles					
125505	P3	FL310	006 F	750ms	1000ms	Dark view				[+13C]	
125516			↑			Start running					
125714	P3 ↗	FL310	"	"	"	Recommend P3					
125946	P3/2.1	FL330	"	"	"	End P3 extract R 2.1				still water main C ₁ /C _s layer	
1305	CONTAMINATING HERE						[SWS Temp +14°C, ALL PARTICLES ON]				
13						✓ Few particles here. CPI seeing nothing					
130702						→ CPI seeing few particles.					
130718						o/h Chilbolton					
130847	END 2.1	FL310	"	"	"	End R 2.1 Turn ↘				[+14C]	
			STILL CONTAMINATING								

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B 150** Date **15/12/05** Operator(s) **DRK** log page **5** of **7**

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	MIRR Pos	Int Times		Remarks
				Vis	NIR	

(SAMPLE PERIOD 0.1 sec THROUGHOUT)

131113		FL330	006(F)	750m	1000m	Dark View Cal
131124		"	↑	"	"	Restart measuring
131418		FL330				Start P4
131549	P4	FL340	"	"	"	End P4 [SAT. o/h]
131847	R3.1	FL340	006(F)	750	1000	Dark Cal view
131859			↑			Restart measuring
131950				→		V. small counts on 2DC Nothing seen on CPI
132220						Drops/side released [+14°C]
132304	3.1	FL340	"	750	1000	End W. at FL340 (Turning at W end of leg)
133001	PS ↑	FL340	"	750	1000	Start PS ↑ FL340 to FL350 [+13°C]
133116			"	1000m	1000m	Dark Cal view
133129			"	"	"	Restart measuring/running
133304	PS/f.1	FL350	"	"	"	End PS & Start R4.1
133540						CPI shows few 'columns' here. Steady increase in Vis spectrum/ counts along this run CPI bullet rockets / 2DC v. small counts of small ice
133850				←		o/h Chills WIND 352°/37 m/sec [+13°C]
134005	f.1	FL350	"	"	"	End R4.1 Turning ↓
134553			"	1000	1000	Dark Cal view
134605						Restart measurement
134620	Start					o/h Chills
134642	f.2	FL350	006(F)	700	1000	Start R4.2 [+12°C] (Peltiers 1 & 2 off)
135040			↑			2DC - few small particles
135514	f.2	FL350	"	600	1000	End R4.2, turning ↓
135920	/	FL350	"	1000	1000	Dark view [+14°C]
135930	/	"	"	"	"	Start measurement (ALL Peltiers on)

750 1000 500 1000 200 1000

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 150	Date	15/12/05		Operator(s)	JEX		log page	6 of 7	
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks				
				Vis	NIR					

140131	P6	FL350	006°(F) ↑	1000	1000	Start P6 ↓ FL350 to FL280				
						Centrales now stopped at FL31,300				
						Clouds : 7/8 Ci(s) above 1-2% Sc.	} viewed from SWS position			
						TC Cumulus				
140812	P6 ↓	FL280	"			Interrupt P6 turning At 40° bank, clipping, at vis 1000m				
141001	P6	FL280	"	"	"	Resume P6] Integ ² time Temp +14°C]			
141030	"		006°(F)	1000	1000	Dark Cal view				
141045	"		↑			Normal view				
141319		FL260				End P6				
141606	PRE-orbits	FL260	"	750	1000	Start Dark Cal view				
141618			"	750	"	Back to run.				
141704	ORBIT 4					Start orbit 4) 60° bank (030°) ↓ 55° bank. ↓ 50°			
141823	ORBIT 4	FL260	"	"	"	Mod [Clipping]				
141851		FL260	"	500	1000	Start Dark View				
141905			"	"	"	Back to run.				
	START									
141957	ORBIT 5	"		500	1000	Start orbit 5 (50°)) 350			
						Minor clipping at start of orbit only				
142131	ORBIT 5	"		"	"	End orbit 5				
142157		FL260	"	250	1000	Start Dark View				
142208		"	"	250	1000	Start Running				
	START									
142300	ORBIT 6	"	"	250	1000	Start orbit 6) 240° (Max 387k counts)			
142427	END 11	"	"	"	"	End " "				
142448		"	"	"	"	Start Dark View				
142508		"	"	"	"	Start Running				
142534	P7 ↓	FL260	"	250	1000	Start P7				
142650	"	"	"	1000	1000	Start Dark View (x2)				
142704	"	"	"	1000	1000	Start Running (vis to 6 counts)				
142819						Interrupt P7 at FL320] Temp +12°C Filters 120 off]			

AIRCRAFT
 ZENITH
 7908

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	15/12/05	Flight	B150	log pages
Operator(s)	none	Campaign	CAESAR			
Departure	Cranfield	Arrival	Cranfield			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						
FERA on	at time					
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	°C	Ch	°C	Ch18	°C
Temperature controller set points		°C	17	°C	-20	°C
MARSS CPU on	at time				Approx 0920	
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Scanning on (LMD box)	at time				Approx 0920	
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers	Not operated				
Turn on Deimos CPU					
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***					
Start Deimos Software	at time				
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold		
Target heating					
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual	
Weather	Cloud		Precip		
	Surface		Pressure		
	Other				

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	0932	
Brightness temps 'sensible'					
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot		Cold	
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold	
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B	
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)

Power changeover

Headset on before start	
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)	
Exit Deimos Software (x)	
POWER CHANGEOVER	
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton
Restart Deimos Software	
System running again	at time

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B 150**

Date: 15th December 2005

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	N	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	N
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	Y		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y		
FWVS	Y	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	Y
“ Red	Y	CVI	N
“ Silicon	Y		
“ JN02	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	N
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	N
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	N
“ JN02	Y	AMS	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	Y		
MARSS	Y		
DEIMOS	Y	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	Y	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	N
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	Y	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	N
ORAC	N	NOxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B150

Date: 15th December 2005

Instruments

1. SID 1 – lost it at 1115, keeps crashing.
2. PCASP – 1st 2 channels noisy from 11:56
3. Flight Manager's PC – locked up at end of Orbit 3. Rebooted, then okay.
4. Flight Summary (and Derived Data Window) Time 2 seconds slow compared to AMTG time. The non-core instruments use AMTG as the "standard" time.

Instrument Status

TAFTS – u/s

ARIES – running unusually slow, restart it at 1056. Improved by 1136 but still drops down to slow rate occasionally

SWS, ARIES, MARSS, Sonde, FWVS – okay

CPI – some errors at end of final profile, probably too warm, otherwise okay

CCN – training went okay. Very little data because of high level.

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom H Calls

Nil

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B150:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics In Flight	
Cloud Physics Processing	
Core Chemistry	pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log
CPI	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
TAFTS	No log is ever taken for TAFTS
CCN	Very little data collected so possibly no log taken.

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

4 x Forward Facing Cameras
4 x Down/Rearward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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